

Advanced Process Monitoring and Control for CFRP RTM in Aerospace without compromises

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ABSTRACT

Resin resistivity has been used successfully at industrial scale for sensing resin arrival, viscosity and online glass transition temperature in the whole range of composites manufacturing [1, 2, 3]. However, in dielectric cure monitoring, the existence of carbon fibres has been always creating a challenging environment i.e. measuring the exceptionally low conductivity of the resin into a highly conductive carbon fibres environment. So when using conventional dielectric sensors, a glass fabric is added to isolate the sensing area from the carbon fibres. However, in 2019 a new type of dielectric durable cure sensor that doesn't need any protection from carbon fibres, was launched and tested successfully [4] in the production of CFRP curved panels. Furthermore, in the Morpho project, using a similar concept, a new resin arrival-only sensor has been developed to cope with carbon fibres and together with other innovations are implemented in a challenging RTM aerospace application. For the real-time provision of resin viscosity, an extensive study of the correlation between resistivity and viscosity evolution as well as the effect of storage aging to both the viscosity and resistivity have been studied with the aim to provide an online viscosity estimation during injection together with the glass transition temperature online estimation during curing. The system has been used in a series of injection trials at Safran Composites showing very promising results to cut cycle time by 15 %.

Keywords: Online Monitoring, Online control, CFRP

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1. INTRODUCTION

In aerospace, the development of liquid composite moulding has been based mostly on trial and error because of the lack of non-intrusive process monitoring means. Although the advancement of dielectric sensing has helped engineers to gain insight of the closed moulding conditions, the existence of carbon fibres in contact with the sensors has significantly limited their adoption at industrial level in CFRP structures.

Besides the significant effort that has been devoted in conventional dielectric (AC) cure monitoring technology for more than 30 years, only laboratory and very limited industrial scale applications exist. On the other hand, the DC-based dielectric cure monitoring technology that was presented in 2010 [5] with the Optimold and Optiflow systems and a clear focus on industrial applications has been proven very successful. The Optimold system is capable of measuring directly the resin's electrical resistance and temperature, while combined with specialised sensors can follow the full

transformation of a thermoset resin i.e. from very low viscous resins at high temperatures to fully cured resins at low temperatures when the resistance ranges between $10^5\Omega$ and $10^{14}\Omega$. A comparison between the DC and AC cure monitoring systems has demonstrated the superiority of the DC technology in sensing the complete transformation of thermoset resins. Furthermore, the DC-based system is cheaper, easy to use and particularly reliable and robust as it has been proven in various industrial installations in wind energy, automotive and aerospace production lines [1, 2, 3, 6]. Last but not least, in contrast to the AC dielectric technology, the DC-based sensing is significantly less vulnerable to carbon fibres due to its inherited superficial electric field so with an appropriate sensor design, it can be used in industrial CFRP production without any extra protection [4]. All the durable sensors [4] have an integrated Pt temperature sensor measuring accurately the temperature close to the resin, which in conjunction with the resistivity is being used for the online estimation of the resin's viscosity and glass transition temperature (T_g), the most important properties in composites processing.

2. INTELLIGENT PROCESS MONITORING IN RTM

In aerospace, RTM is being used every day practically without real-time information from the mould cavity beside a few mould temperatures and injection pressure. However, it is obvious that any real-time information of the resin position and state from inside the cavity would help significantly in the development, process optimisation and the online quality control of the manufacturing process. For example, knowing how the resin flows inside the cavity would help improving the accuracy of simulation methods and understand the process deviations and defects, while using this information in real-time could lead to control actions that could reduce repairs or scrap rate. Furthermore, the use of cure sensors could give better insight of how the viscosity evolves during the injection and packing, while the online provision of the Glass Transition Temperature (T_g) could lead to shorter cure cycles.

One of the objectives of the Morpho project (<https://morpho-h2020.eu/>), is to gain real-time information of the resin status in the mould cavity and around the mould to ensure optimum process control in real-time for RTM aerospace applications. In this framework, a variety of dielectric sensors have been developed and installed in a RTM mould for a typical aerospace part for turbines, while an intelligent system is gathering all the measurements in real-time to transform them to useful process parameters and to lead to necessary control actions.

The main components of this intelligent system are analysed below.

2.1 Dielectric sensors

The inline resin arrival sensor (fig. 1) is connected to the Optiflow unit (resin arrival and temperature monitoring) and can provide the resin arrival time-stamp when the resin flows through the sensor. The inline sensor can be easily integrated at the inlet and outlet gates without any major mould modification to record when the resin enters or exits the mould cavity.

Figure 1. The inline resin arrival sensor for the inlet and outlet gates of the RTM tool.

The CF durable cure sensor (fig. 2) was developed [4] for use in direct contact with carbon fibres without the need of any insulation. Its performance has been verified in the production of CFRP panels for an automotive application [2] with compression pressures up to $20 \cdot 10^6 \text{ N/m}^2$. Although in the current application, lower injection pressure has been used, the considerably higher curing temperature, the longer processing cycles and the higher fibre volume content, have created more challenging conditions for this sensor. Furthermore, a new housing with reduced length specifically for the Morpho project was developed and used.

Figure 2. The CF cure durable sensor.

Although the CF cure sensor provides also resin arrival information, it was decided to develop a dedicated sensor that can work in direct contact with carbon fibres providing only the resin arrival information. The sensor that was developed in the Morpho project (fig. 3) has an improved manufacturability and significantly lower cost than the CF cure sensor and it is suitable for the high Fibre Volume fractions that are found in aerospace. At the same time, the sensor works with the Optiflow unit, resulting in a particularly affordable solution especially when numerous such sensors are needed.

Figure 3. Close-up of the new CF resin arrival sensor, installed flush-mounted in the tool at Safran Composites, Itteville.

2.2 The monitoring units

Each cure sensor is connected to an Optimold unit, while up to 4 resin arrival sensors are connected to an Optiflow unit. Both Optimold and Optiflow units are DC-based dielectric systems, which measure directly the electrical resistance, however Optimold can measure up to 100 Tohm,

covering the whole range of curing of any thermoset resin processed at temperatures higher than 40°C. As can be seen at the left of fig. 4, at the present application there is a stacking of Optimold and Optiflow units to handle all the sensors that are being used to monitor the state of resin at several locations in the mould cavity. On the right of fig. 4, the front-end touch-screen, placed at the top, in front of the press is shown.

Figure 4. Left: The Cure Simulator and the stacking of Optimold and Optiflow units for the current application. Right: the front-end HMI screen (top) at the front of the press.

Figure 5. The Cure Simulator concept for a RTM application.

2.3 The Cure Simulator

The Cure Simulator concept has been developed in a previous EC funded project [6] to provide a non-intrusive solution for monitoring the curing in autoclaves. As can be seen in fig. 5, the idea is to monitor the curing of the resin in the mould by proxy i.e. the temperature of the same resin sample that takes place in the Cure Simulator's resin cell, is following accurately the temperature measured in real-time at the point of interest, for example, in the autoclave or the mould cavity.

The same concept has been also used to provide the Tg during the cure of epoxy adhesives in wind turbine blade assembly. In both cases, the use of the Cure Simulator enables the quantitative cure monitoring where it was challenging or impossible to introduce a non-intrusive cure sensor. In the present RTM application, the use of the Cure Simulator can offer an alternative means that can provide more information about resin aging/ mixing ratio, viscosity and curing in a more secure environment, especially if mould's modifications should be avoided. Furthermore, in the Morpho project, there is the opportunity to study further the suitability of the Cure Simulator to provide valuable information comparing it to the in-situ sensors that have been installed in the mould cavity.

2.4 The Online Resin State software

Last but not least, the Online Resin State software has been developed to cope with the epoxy resin that has been used in the Morpho project. To ensure the accuracy of the online estimation, a series of trials were initially performed at Synthesites laboratories and a number of DMA coupons were produced and analysed by Safran Composites. Furthermore, the correlation between viscosity and resistivity was established for the online viscosity. The ORS software together with the Human-Machine-Interface and the data acquisition software run at the central All-in-one PC, shown in fig. 4, right. The software handles all the communication with the different modules and is able to provide also the control actions to any digital or analog device.

3. RESULTS

In the present application, the mono-component epoxy resin 2896 from 3M has been used for the demonstration of the intelligent monitoring system in the manufacturing of a FOD (Foreign Object Debris) curved panel (fig. 6) in a steel RTM mould that has been designed and manufactured by Safran Composites, specifically for the Morpho project. The dry carbon-fibre 3D preform was woven while in some injections, additional optical fibres were also introduced in the framework of the Morpho R&D project.

Figure 6. The FOD panel

Following the lab-scale development and the calibration, the complete system was installed at Safran Composites as can be seen in fig. 4. In fig. 7, an overview of the information that is provided

by each tool-integrated sensor is depicted: besides resin arrival timestamp at several locations (green dots), the cure sensors (orange and red dots) measure the electrical resistance of the resin providing real-time information about the resin age/mixing ratio, viscosity, gelation and Tg as shown in fig. 7.

Figure 7. Overview of the sensors and monitoring units used in the intelligent process monitoring system (Green: Resin arrival and temp, Brown: Cure, Red: Cure Simulator).

Three cure and thirteen resin arrival durable CF sensors were installed flush mounted at the bottom tool as can be seen in fig.8. Two more inline sensors were installed at the inlet and outlet gates, together with a pressure sensor and the Cure Simulator.

Figure 8. The bottom tool with all sixteen in-mould sensors installed.

Until now, six panels have been produced. In fig. 9 the resin arrival times during an injection are shown. Resin arrival is depicted when the timeline bar colour change from green to yellow.

Figure 9. Resin arrival time-stamps during resin injection.

Based on this resin arrival information, the flow front advancement can be speculated for each injection and can be seen in fig. 10. In all of them, there is a distinct race-tracking across a step that exists in the cavity and is depicted by a blue line. But besides that, several other flow front patterns were identified especially in the 3rd, 4th and 5th injection due to specific preform issues (fig.10).

Figure 10. Flow patterns for the 6 injections already performed at Safran Composites

The narrow variation of the temperature (2°C) which is being measured by the numerous cure and resin arrival sensors across the mould, ensures the very good temperature homogeneity across the mould cavity. It is very encouraging that none of the 16 sensors showed any issue or interference from the carbon fibres during the whole duration of the production cycles. On the other hand, the resistance curves measured by the three cure sensors show some variation with respect to the Cure Simulator which is under investigation.

3.1 Online Cycle Optimisation

A fixed cure cycle is being widely used in advanced composites manufacturing to ensure part quality at the expense of cost. In most cases the fixed cure cycle includes multiple safety factors which decrease considerably its productivity without particular improvement in quality. In the Morpho project, the introduction of the real-time process information allows for optimizing each cycle based on the feedback from the sensors by pushing the process to its limits. For example, we can use two criteria to pass from one stage to the next as depicted in fig.11. The completion of the filling and the significant increase of viscosity can trigger the start of the heating sooner than the fixed duration of the injection while the achievement of the target T_g can trigger the start of cooling. In this way, around 20% cycle time can be saved.

Figure 11. The original temperature profile (blue) against the optimised profile (orange) maintaining the injection and curing temperatures.

We can further optimise the cycle time, by increasing the main processing temperatures as depicted in fig. 12, always using the sensors to ensure the good quality of the part. In this case, a further 15% cycle time reduction can be achieved.

Figure 12. The original temperature profile (blue) against the optimised profile (orange) with increased injection and curing temperatures to further cut down cycle time.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A complete monitoring and intelligent control of the RTM process for carbon fibre components has been implemented successfully. Nineteen durable sensors have been used to monitor viscosity, resin arrival and curing during RTM production. The new CF sensors have proven their robustness at industrial conditions while the Cure Simulator can provide additional information of curing at locations where we cannot place cure sensors.

The Morpho project is on-going and further trials will be executed to gain a complete insight of the process and how these sensors can be used to optimise production in a robust way. Furthermore, new improved sensors are under development and will be also tested in the remaining period of the project.

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